

TITANIUM ENHANCED SINTERING THROUGH LIQUID PHASE SINTERING

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1 General Introduction

Titanium has good specific strength and corrosion resistance at a broad working temperature which makes it attractive for use in many aerospace, automotive, and biomedical applications. However, its high processing cost limits its use greatly. The net shape production of powder-metallurgy reduces material waste and cost from machining. Ti sintering is in current use and shows further potential to reduce cost of parts. The use of 1) blended elemental Aluminium in reactive Liquid Phase Sintering (LPS) of Ti and 2) TiH₂ powders enhance densification at low temperatures. With the reduction of sintering temperatures through enhanced sintering, titanium product costs are hoped to be reduced for broader industrial application. This current investigation aims to achieve fully dense titanium through sintering blended elemental Ti/TiH₂-Al powders at low temperatures, thus reducing processing costs, and achieve industrially applicable mechanical properties.

2 Theory and Experiments

2.1 Liquid Phase Sintering

Liquid Phase Sintering is an enhanced sintering method in which a secondary element becomes liquid during sintering while the primary element remains solid. Densification is enhanced firstly by liquid flow and rearrangement and capillary action, then also through rapid solid-liquid diffusion, and solution reprecipitation. In this investigation, the sintering of titanium is of interest, and aluminium is used as the secondary liquid phase which is a common element in Ti-alloys and melts at a lower temperature than normal Ti sintering temperatures of approximately 1400°C. During sintering atomic diffusion will occur at the Ti-Al solid-liquid interface to form intermetallics, where TiAl₃ has

been shown to form preferentially in this situation [1]. It is predicted that a Ti particle matrix will be surrounded by Ti-Aluminide reinforcement forming a metallic composite. However, the formation of such a composite depends on the diffusion that is allowed to occur by the sintering parameters designed.

2.2 TiH₂ powders

TiH₂ powders have been shown to dehydrogenate during sintering to form a pure Ti final product and it is proposed that the exposed active Ti surfaces enhance sintering [2]. The hydrogenation of titanium makes it brittle and it can be milled to form a fine Ti hydride powder. In this investigation TiH₂ powders are used to help the formation of a dense Ti part at reduced sintering temperatures. Depending on the size of the powder, during sintering the dehydrogenation process can occur at low temperatures below 600°C [2]. In this investigation it is hoped that TiH₂ powder can be used as a matter of convenience and to enhance sintering at low temperatures below 700°C. The interaction of the simultaneous use of a liquid Al phase will be important, because dehydrogenation is expected to be nearly complete before the melting of the Al phase, and experimentation will be required to see the ability of Al to flow through the Ti powder if the powder has begun to densify.

2.3 Experiments

Ti sponge was hydrogenated at 450-500°C under a pressurised hydrogen atmosphere until hydrogen absorption ceased. The TiH₂ sponge was then planetary ball milled with a 10:1 stainless steel ball:powder mass ratio under a hydrogen or argon atmosphere, and handled in a argon glove box. Various commercial Al powders from mean diameter 12 µm to 86 µm were mixed with Ti or

TiH₂ powders in a 3D mixer for 30 minutes. The powders were then hot-press sintered in a 6mm diameter graphite mould in an induction furnace under a primary vacuum at temperatures from 600-700°C at 80 MPa for 30 minutes. The percentage aluminium was varied at 0, 5, 10, 20 atomic percent.

2.4 Discussion and Results

The relative densities of the sintered specimens using pure Ti powder are compared to those using TiH₂ in Fig. 1. Under the experimental conditions set the Ti-Al specimens densify well at low percentages of aluminium. The specimens which use TiH₂ powders densify at 0 at% Al while poor densification is seen when pure Ti powder is used. XRD results detect no hydride titanium remaining. However, because the mechanical properties of titanium are sensitive to trace amounts of hydrogen the amount of hydrogen should be quantified.

Figure 1. Relative densities of sintered Ti and TiH₂ powders with varied atomic percentages of Al.

The microstructure achieved using TiH₂ powder during the experiments performed show dense Ti areas and porous areas surrounded by Ti-Al intermetallics, shown in Fig. 2, despite enhanced densification.

2.6 Further work

The final form of the composite and the amount and type of intermetallics formed will depend on diffusion, and hence, the sintering parameters used. Sintering has been performed with consistent parameters, and experimental variation of parameters will be studied. The detailed chemical analysis of the specimens will be carried out to

evaluate the extent of dehydrogenation during sintering and the quantity of impurities. Final mechanical testing will be performed to determine the mechanical properties of the metallic composite formed.

Figure 2. SEM micrograph of a sintered TiH₂-20at%Al specimen.

3 Conclusion

The enhanced sintered methods of LPS and the use of hydride titanium during sintering are investigated to reduce the sintering temperature and thus cost of titanium parts. In this investigation enhanced densification has been seen at low temperature, and further experimentation is required to achieve an optimal titanium specimen.

References

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